

Revolution will not be televised,
it will be tweeted

Media and Democracy in the Digitalisation Age

Abridged version of the TA-SWISS study «Medien und Meinungsmacht»

Abridged version of the TA-SWISS study «Medien und Meinungsmacht» which has been realized with the support of the Federal Office of Communications (OFCOM).

Medien und Meinungsmacht

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Media and democracy in a few words

Only those who are well informed can make informed decisions. In a direct democracy, in which citizens have to vote on complex issues at the ballot box, comprehensive, balanced information is essential. Quality media thus provide the lubricant that keeps the cogs of the political machine running smoothly. But the media sector is in upheaval: advertisements, which were still contributing a large part of the publishing houses' income pot in the 1990s and together with sales revenue were thus co-financing journalistic output, have been switched to the Internet. Search engines and social media such as Facebook or Twitter in particular, which contribute no added value themselves, have taken over a large proportion of advertising. News and data are accessible for free on the Internet around the clock. And the free newspapers launched since the late 1990s are also undercutting the model of the paid-for daily and weekly newspaper. The question that arises is how the new information channels impact on the political culture in Switzerland and how high-quality journalism can be funded in the future.

The opportunities ...

Access to politically relevant information has multiplied. Reports and announcements are no longer published exclusively by established broadcasters and newspapers, but are also distributed via social networks and short messaging systems (SMS) and displayed by search engines. Young people on a tight budget in particular can get information free of charge thanks to free newspapers and the Internet.

Digital media open up potential for new and interesting forms of journalistic communication: text, photos, moving images, soundtracks and interactive graphics can be interlinked with attractive forms of narration and presentation.

Anybody can reach the general public via the Internet. Lesser-known politicians who find it difficult to bring their points of view into the media address the general public directly via Twitter and Facebook or via their own blogs. And the new means of communication are open to the public as well: newspapers' Internet forums publish reactions from their readers and anyone can participate in the political debate with their own comments via social media. Political communication is becoming interactive, and all interested parties are finding a mouthpiece.

... the risks ...

To compensate for the dwindling revenue from the advertising and reader market, publishing houses are changing their business models. Commercial considerations are endangering journalistic independence, and if editorial offices lack the resources for their own research there is an increasing temptation to take up third-party reports – including from PR agencies. There is a growing risk of content from less transparent sources finding its way into reports without further verification.

When news is spread via social media or search engines, the selection criteria remain obscure, because the underlying algorithms are secret. Members of the public don't know why a report appears in first place, which makes it all the more difficult for them to evaluate the relevance and quality of the reporting.

... and some recommendations

Even in the Internet age, democracies rely on the journalistic services of media organisations. In view of the changes in the media, an infrastructure programme for journalism is therefore urgently needed.

From the political viewpoint, independent journalism should be encouraged, in order to safeguard the prerequisites for independent media services. Private media – whether online or offline – should be able to benefit from direct media promotion. In addition, an independent public service provider must be maintained. To reach a young public, this should be active online without restrictions and be able to broadcast innovative video as well as audio offerings. By contrast, there is some justification in avoiding advertising and sponsorship. Moreover, ownership by foundations and employees, for example, which reduces the economic pressure on editors, could be supported by tax incentives or by tax-exempt donations.

Politicians, the media and the population must actively campaign for all citizens to have media skills and to be in a position to assess the quality and worth of journalistic offerings. Schools have a key role to play here.

The media must be required to maintain transparency. Media organisations should undertake to prevent the mixing of journalistic and commercial interests and to publish ownership structures. Governance of the algorithms of new media is also essential.

Good politics needs balanced information

Far-reaching political decisions require balanced and comprehensive knowledge. In a direct democracy, in which the country's political destiny is determined by its citizens at the ballot box, quality media play a crucial role in informing the general public. But the economic basis of the independent media is disintegrating and the sector is being challenged to re-invent itself.

Explosive political power is inherent in printed and published news items. The rulers of Europe in the early modern era were very well aware of this fact. Until the 1830s journalism was therefore still under the control of the authorities, who monitored the content of newspapers and granted them financial subsidies.

Only gradually, as state monopolies on advertising were reduced and taxes on advertising abolished, did the European press gain its independence. In Switzerland, freedom of the press was enshrined in the constitution when the Federal State was founded in 1848, and this led to the establishment of numerous regional and national newspapers – some of which were tied to religious or political interests, some independent. From the end of the 19th century, investments in new technologies such as rotary printing and typesetting machines necessitated increased funding of the press through advertising. This in turn enabled the selling price of newspapers to fall, and hence to reach a wider public. Radio and television, which from the 1950s reached an ever greater public, did nothing to fundamentally change the economic symbiosis between journalistic output and advertising revenue.

Free newspapers and the Internet turn the media landscape upside down

The Internet, which gradually became widespread from 1993, and the numerous free newspapers launched after 1999 led to upheaval in the media landscape. Thanks to their ability to target advertising at the appropriate customer base, search engines and social media in particular are outstripping newspapers as the established advertising vehicles, while online offerings from traditional newspapers, along with the new free morning and evening papers, suggest that journalism comes for free.

The shifts in the media structure were reflected in the business results. Between 1995 and 2014 the total circulation of paid-for copies of Swiss newspapers fell from 4.26 million to 3.11 million. In the same period, net advertising sales fell sharply by almost 60 percent from CHF 1,675 million to CHF 731 million. The following twelve months saw a further drop to CHF 682 million. In 2014 the advertising revenue of television, at CHF 772 million, exceeded that of the paid-for press for the first time. And just one year later, advertising on the Web recorded the highest earnings, at CHF 870 million. However, it is search engines and online classified markets, rather than journalistic offerings, that account for the lion's share of online advertising. Online advertising is therefore far from being able to compensate for the decline in print advertising.

Publishing houses and media companies are using a variety of strategies to counter the financial difficulties. One of these is aimed at pooling strengths, generating synergies and thus saving costs. The consequences: among the print media, which are having to curtail the particularly high cost of manufacturing their products, there are now few providers dominating the scene. The

three most powerful publishing houses have acquired around 80 percent of the daily circulation in German-speaking Switzerland and as much as 88 percent in French-speaking areas.

Savings are also being made in journalistic output. Many newspapers have trimmed their network of correspondents, and reporters are shared among various media. If resources for critical verification of information are lacking in editorial offices, however, there is greater reliance on content that is supplied by PR sources. And because of the financial problems, advertising-funded media may hold back on critical reporting if they have to face the fear of offending advertising customers as a result.

Since the start of the social network Facebook in 2004 and the micro-blogging service Twitter two years later, news can also be brought to the public independently of established media. In principle, anyone and everyone can circulate their concerns to a wide audience via such channels. These channels are increasingly being used in politics: one-third of Swiss Parliamentarians now have a Twitter account. Members of the social democrat party SP are particularly active here (at 35 percent), followed by those of the Christian democrat CVP (33 percent). Ten percent of the Swiss People's Party SVP's members of parliament are active «Tweeters».

The shifts in the media landscape could not fail to impact on political debate in Switzerland. The question is, which media provide information in which way about which topics – and who they reach.

Media study by TA-SWISS: Independence under scrutiny

When the media become economically dependent, there is a risk that they will no longer provide information freely and no longer select their topics primarily based on the criteria of journalistic relevance. However, that will have consequences for democracy. The TA-SWISS study therefore highlights which topics are being taken up by both established and new media, which actors are having their say and how political discussions are expressed in the different communication channels. Part of the study also looks specifically at media consumption in the 16 to 25 age group. The study «Medien und Meinungsmacht» (Media and the power to shape opinions) was carried out by a project group of academics at the Universities of Fribourg, Lausanne and Zürich led by Manuel Puppis and Michael Schenk of the University of Fribourg. The Federal Office of Communications OFCOM contributed to the funding of the study.

Different priorities for different media

The Internet provides a highly diverse group of people the facility to circulate their concerns, while for their part the established media report topics that very much follow the political agenda. However, it is evident from surveys which problems particularly preoccupy the population. Depending on the channel, different levels of urgency are attributed to these factual issues.

Every year a wide-ranging survey registers the concerns of the Swiss population. This «worry barometer» is based on responses from over 1000 representatively selected persons. For years, the three topics «migration», «unemployment» and «retirement planning» have come out on top on a surprisingly steady basis. The dialogue over energy topics takes up the middle ground, together with financial issues about the economy, federal finances and bank secrecy, as well as terrorism, extremism, xenophobia and racism.

The study by TA-SWISS investigated whether, and how strongly, the concerns of the population were also represented in the media and in political circles. To determine the political agenda, over the summer and autumn session of 2015 a wide range of documents were evaluated, such as the Official Bulletin of the Federal Assembly or parties' Facebook postings. The choice of topics in the established media was determined by analysing the content of reports from various printed newspapers – from free newsheets and tabloid newspapers to national daily newspapers – together with the news websites of SRF and RTS. Finally, the project group also assessed the communication that had been sent via the short messaging service Twitter over two 2-week investigation periods in the early summer and autumn of 2015.

Established media as a mirror of politics

The population, media and politicians are largely preoccupied with identical topics. There is, however, a clear distinction in the value placed on these. Despite similar topics and problems, their ranking or prioritisation can therefore differ substantially in each case.

The prioritisation of topics by politicians largely coincides with that of the established media. In the early summer of 2015 the main focus, both in everyday political business, as well as in the national newspapers and in the SRG's online offering, was on public finances and taxation. Traffic and mobility issues, and economic development also rank in the top ten in the agenda of both politicians and the traditional media.

Compared to the early summer, by the autumn the prioritisation of topics shifted only slightly. The debate over the problem of refugees and asylum now gained in importance, and now comes first (political agenda) and second (media agenda). In the early summer, this topic was still only in 7th place on the political agenda and did not even figure in the canon of the established media. Six of the topics that were taken up by the media in the autumn were already on their agenda in the early summer. It is worth noting here that the prioritisation of the Swiss Broadcasting Corporation SRG SSR only matches the political agenda in the early summer; during the election campaign in the autumn it focuses on other content and is less influenced by the political campaigns than the established press.

The free newspapers and short messaging service Twitter focus on rather different issues. In the autumn both look similar, during the election campaign, focusing much more on the content priorities of the political agenda than in the early summer. During «normal

parliamentary business» however, there was no discernible agreement with the political agenda on the ranking of topics. On Twitter in particular in the election campaign more topics from the political agenda are taken up in official communication.

Who's listening to what the people have to say

The concerns of the population – especially on issues about health and health insurance schemes, but also about the refugee and asylum problem and energy policy – will in all likelihood be given equal priority by the national daily newspapers and the Sunday press. At least for the investigation period in the autumn there was evidence of a significant connection, while in the early summer the rankings by the media and population agendas do not agree.

The free press and tabloid newspapers deal with the same topics, but treat them as less important than the population. The public broadcaster SRG SSR also sets different priorities from the population.

Twitter, on the other hand, is dominated, especially in the autumn during the election campaign, by a variety of topics that are of burning importance to the population. It is striking that a stand is taken on Twitter on a range of topics and concerns that were already being generally discussed in the spring. Twitter is thus taking on a key role in opinion forming, in that topics and concerns from the public debate are tackled, which thus stimulates the political discussion in Switzerland.

Established media risk alienation

The established media – national newspapers and the SRG SSR – play a decisive role in reinforcing the political debate, and they also exert a considerable

influence on public opinion in the election campaign. By contrast, the topics that preoccupy the population are only inadequately reflected in reports from the regional newspapers, the free newspapers and the SRG SSR. This creates the risk that it will be difficult for media users to continue to identify their own interests and experiences in the reporting, and the media offering will become increasingly alien to them.

Active users of the short messaging service Twitter pay more attention to the concerns of the population, which thus enables them to have a certain influence on the political agenda of the established media. Because the traditional media are also aware of Twitter, this new channel opens up new possibilities for the general public to bring topics that are important to them into the media discourse.

Multi-voice chorus of opinion from old and new media

Press, radio and television were long regarded as «gatekeepers» of public opinion: they set the topics that were talked about by the public, and they also selected the personalities whom they allowed to express their views. The new media also give new voices a hearing.

In June 2015 the Swiss people voted on whether retroactively from 2012 a 20 percent tax should be imposed on estates and gifts of more than CHF 2 million. Two-thirds of the revenue was to go to the old age and survivors' insurance fund, and the remaining third was earmarked for the cantons. The clear defeat of the proposal was preceded by a months-long heated debate. This provided the TA-SWISS study with the material to pinpoint which political actors used which channels to voice which arguments. Interest was centred on comparing the traditional media with the new online offerings such as social networks or search engines.

Twitter's contribution to democracy ...

In the traditional media, on Twitter and in the Google search results, the comments from politicians come out on top: around one-third of all statements come from the parties and their staff, who therefore control the public discussion. What is new, though, is that «second rank» politicians also have a voice on Twitter – that is, persons who are not among the figureheads of their party and who are rarely or never called to speak to the established media.

In second place in the established media and on the websites found on Google about the initiative are press releases from the initiators as well as those from groups that are fighting against the initiative. Their public resonance is, however, only about half as great as that for the parties' spokespersons.

In the short messaging service Twitter, however, a different kind of actor gets a chance. In this case, as well as the party members it is «other actors» who control the field. They comprise mainly traditional media who also distribute their reports on the initiative via Twitter. Finally, following in third place, but still with 12 percent, are the «ordinary citizens», whose voices are not heard at all in the traditional media and only in individual cases on the websites presented by Google. Twitter is thus proving to be a democratic medium: it allows access to the general public by citizens who are not only able to express themselves via short messaging services but are also noticed.

... and its argumentative weaknesses

A total of 42 different arguments were presented for or against the initiative. The most complete coverage of all these was by the national daily and Sunday newspapers, the SRG SSR and the websites displayed by Google: at over 95 percent the arguments for and against were almost fully covered in these media.

Twitter users, however, referred only to just over two-thirds of the arguments. Also, compared to the established media considerably fewer experts had anything to say: these are largely absent from the popular microblog in connection with the referendum campaign being examined.

All media investigated concentrated on a limited number of arguments. Among the traditional providers – the national press and the SRG SSR – the top ten arguments make up just under half of all explanations. In this respect too, however, Twitter goes its own way: half of the tweets contain no argument at all. Being limited to 140 characters does, of course, only provide limited space for entering reasoning and explanations.

Communication via Twitter might therefore be of use primarily for exchanging views with like-minded people and to find support for one's own opinion.

A new channel for differing opinions

In the traditional media, supporters of the initiative were heard rather more than its opponents: over 36 percent of the people quoted approved the new tax, while a little more than 26 percent opposed it. The remaining comments could not be assigned to any camp. The websites listed by Google also give rather more weight to the pro-camp at around 30 percent than to the opponents of the initiative (26 percent).

On Twitter, however, sympathies were split the other way round. A little over 38 percent of the Tweets circulated came from opponents of the initiative, while supporters were never more than 18 percent. The cross-party committee that opposed the proposal therefore made use of social media for a successful campaign, and the result at the ballot box corresponded to the relative strengths of the pro and contra votes on Twitter. However, the extent to which the short messaging service was actually able to influence the referendum result cannot be determined from the data.

It is clear however that the new media enable political actors and interest groups to address the general public directly and to campaign for ideas that are only presented in watered down form. This finding is double-edged for democracy, because it is not only spontaneous citizens' movements that can make use of this communication forum: well-heeled professionally organised lobbies can too. It is all the more important that the established media, as the mediating authority, strike a balance between the extreme positions.

No reason to fear parallel segments of the public

If Google refers to web pages that provide information about the inheritance tax, or SMS messages about the proposal are sent via Twitter, it is often the established media that supply the material for them. More than a quarter of all Tweets and almost one-third of the Google search results on the subject refer to reports by the mass media.

Radio broadcasters and newspaper firms that are now also present on the Web with online news portals are thus gaining coverage, in that their content is distributed further and interlinked by the new media. This content is therefore a long way from being used exclusively to develop concerned, autonomous segments of the public and thus to promote the formation of parallel societies. It is rather the case that the traditional and younger media refer to each other reciprocally and thus produce a true «integrated network public».

Youth in focus: using media in the future

Young people get information differently from today's generation of over thirty-year-olds. The Internet is the gravitational centre of media usage by 16- to 25-year-olds. Print media are considered provided they are free.

The future belongs to youth. That also applies to the media landscape of the future, which will be shaped by the needs and habits of future generations. The study by TA-SWISS has therefore investigated which channels young people between 16 and 25 years of age mainly use to get information and which topics are the focus of attention.

Mobile and networked

The Internet is the top favourite of young people, outstripping all other media. Ninety-eight percent of 16- to 25-year-olds regularly spend time on the Internet, much more than the Swiss average of 82 percent. It is also worth noting that young people often make disproportionate use of the Internet when travelling, which means on their smartphone.

When young people seek information about politics, however, they pay relatively little attention to radio and the press. Television is used mainly for information about national and international events. Seventy-five percent of 16- to 25-year-olds regularly watch TV, compared to an average 84 among the Swiss population. Nevertheless, these figures should be accepted with caution, because many TV broadcasts can be consumed on a time-delay basis via the Internet and radio broadcasters also make many programmes available to download as podcasts; young people in particular often use a smartphone, tablet or computer to watch television or listen to the radio.

Nevertheless, certain print products can reach out to young people: the free press gets more attention among them than the average for the Swiss population. They also use commuter magazines to find information about day-to-day events.

Better well entertained than politically informed

On a day to day basis, most Swiss youngsters have very little interest in politics. The 2015 youth barometer shows that one in four 16- to 25-year-olds have a (more) serious interest in politics. Media usage confirms the relatively low inclination to concern themselves with local and regional issues, national politics or the economy, and background reports and analyses. The 16- to 25-year-olds prefer to focus on new IT trends, reports about cars and motorcycles, information on education and training, features about fashion, clothes, cosmetics and beauty, as well as reports about celebrities.

If young people watch TV programmes they prefer entertainment formats. In this case, young people tend to favour private broadcasters over what public service broadcasters offer. This picture is confirmed in the case of radio, where – in contrast to the Swiss average – private broadcasters also scored among young people.

The – comparatively rarely read – newspapers are used primarily when young people want to keep up to date on what's happening in their own community; among minors social media are the medium of choice for finding out about events in the local community. For regional matters the young target group gets information from the radio, news portals and TV, while for national issues the television is the favoured source of information.

Exchange of views via social media

For referendums, the Internet is actively used by young people for guidance. During the 2011 to 2015 legislative period, 25 percent of the population obtained information about referendum proposals on the Internet; among young adults between 18 and 29 years old, the figure was much higher, at 45 percent.

The Web is therefore not just an information medium, but also provides a forum for exchanging views. Seventy percent of young Swiss people exchange views via WhatsApp about political events in their community. Social media such as Facebook are much less used for this (40 percent of mentions). Because minors use SMS messages, social networks or even video platforms much more often than young adults to obtain information and exchange views on politics, it must be assumed that in future these channels will continue to grow in importance.

Politics taken at its word

Thanks to appropriate software it is possible to automatically assess and clearly display details of the voting behaviour of members of parliament and other data from the political scene. Such information acts as a guide for the population and motivates them to engage more closely with the candidates. Elections receive new impetus through information technology.

On the electronic platform smartvote, voters can check how well their own profile matches that of the different parties and individual candidates. The idea behind this is that citizens prefer to be represented by personalities whose views are similar to their own. Many Swiss politicians now use smartvote for their own positioning, and the media are also working intensively with online electoral support. The study by TA-SWISS highlights how great an influence such a voting advice app has become, and considers the question of what consequences that might have for democracy. The investigation is based on surveys of smartvote users, political candidates and party leaders.

Not yet used equally by everyone

At the National Council elections in 2011 about 84 percent of the candidates had a smartvote profile. The party leaders and election campaigns recommend candidates to submit a profile and hence acknowledge the significance of the new information tool. However, this is regarded as more important in German-speaking Switzerland than in the French-speaking region, which might be to do with the fact that this is a German-Swiss development. But the fear that smartvote might compete with the parties might contribute to the reticence in western Switzerland.

In the main, smartvote is consulted by people under 45, with those holding a university degree being much more strongly represented than in the population as a whole. Just under one-third of smartvote users are women. The online voting advice app has therefore not yet caught on with the public on a broad front, because it is used mainly by people educated to a higher than average level with a serious interest in politics.

Person more important than party

Smartvote is generating rather more interest in Switzerland than comparable services in other countries. This is because in the local system voters can split their vote and accumulate candidates, which considerably increases the scope.

The greatest influence that smartvote has is on the voters' information base. The voting advice app also motivates them to search for further details about the candidates, and it also emerged that many of the respondents – actually about 30 percent – became more aware of candidates whom they would not otherwise have elected.

Not all those who use the voting advice app give equal weight to the recommendations. About a quarter of respondents attach more importance to party membership than to the responses posted on smartvote by the candidates; for another quarter it is precisely the reverse, while the third quarter considers both equally. The final quarter directly follows the recommendations by smartvote. Moreover, these people also take the view that the candidates would have adhered to the promises they made in the election campaign; other smartvote users, however, allow politicians a certain margin of discretion in the exercise of their mandate.

Voters who are strongly guided by smartvote therefore seem to be able to find a lot that is positive in the so-called delegate model, which is based on the idea that holders of political office would be tied to a mandate and are under obligation to adhere strictly to the positions expressed in the election campaign. This contradicts the model anticipated in the constitution, which gives more freedom to those elected. Among all voters, however, only a minority take this attitude. Smartvote also tends to diminish the importance of the parties compared to the individual candidates. If the use of online voting advice apps continues to spread, it cannot be ruled out that there could be a stronger trend towards the delegate model, with corresponding sanctions for politicians who reserve the right to be able to express their own opinion in the political debate.

Media sector in turmoil

The established media are investing in the digitalisation of their core business and looking for new revenue models and business fields to compensate for the lost income from advertising and newspaper subscriptions. This also involves risks for the media's journalistic output that are highly significant for the functioning of modern democracies.

Digitalisation has transformed both the finances and the production processes of the established media. The authors of the TA-SWISS study have analysed business reports and strategy papers of leading Swiss media in detail, and in detailed qualitative interviews with CEOs and strategists from the largest media firms have also discussed strategies, investments and any conflicts of interest between independent reporting and the desired business models.

Digitalisation of the media business

In virtually all media organisations the order of the day is: economise. Circulations and advertising revenue are falling. At the same time, there are also major investments in new technologies and know-how. This digitalisation of the media firms' core business is crucial for them to hold their own in the changed environment and to produce modern journalism. But as a result there are even fewer resources available in the traditional journalistic sector. The pressure to economise is leading not only to job losses but also encourages cooperation in the editorial field, in printing and with technological solutions.

The media organisations are trying to overcome the turmoil in the media world with a variety of strategies. While the NZZ uses a paywall and is relying on income from readers, the Blick Group and AZ Medien are putting their faith in a range model to generate as much

income as possible with online advertising. Tamedia has paid-for as well as free publications in its portfolio. To achieve higher income, all media firms are also relying on advertising aimed at specific groups and new forms of advertising. Ringier and Tamedia are also generating a substantial part of their sales in new business fields. Also especially promising are online market places such as Homegate, Ricardo or Scout24, as well as e-commerce platforms.

Potentials of digital journalism ...

With regard to the quality of journalistic reporting, the changes in the media sector are raising hopes as well as arousing fears.

Digitalisation is opening up very promising opportunities for journalism. For the reorganisation of editorial offices is not only pursuing the goal of increasing productivity but also developing modern online media products. The multimedia linking of texts with photographic material, video or infographics enables new forms of narrative and presentation.

In addition, social media allow interaction with users. Whether the young generations in particular, who increasingly consume media content online and on mobiles will be reached will depend on such innovative formats. But if the new possibilities for journalism are also used, convergent working may not be an economising measure.

... and challenges for democracy

The changes for the media brought about by digitalisation pose major challenges for journalism and democracy. Editorial cooperation and slimmed-down editorial offices make sense from an economic viewpoint, but

encourage neither regionally varied perspectives on national topics nor in-depth research. Because there is no clear editorial deadline with the Internet and production has to cover different channels, time pressure is increasing in journalism. There could therefore be a greater temptation to take up contributions from third parties – especially from PR agencies – without further editing.

It is not just pressure to economise; business models also affect reporting. For media that are heavily reliant on advertising, there is a risk that critical reports about major advertising clients will only be published with caution. Moreover, new forms of advertising obscure the distinction between advertising and editorial content. And the strategy pursued by diversified media firms, to integrate the different business sectors more intensely, could potentially blur the boundary between «content» (editorial) and «commerce» (advertising department and classified ads) even further. With paywalls, however, the risk is that less wealthy sections of the population will be excluded from high quality information and will have to make do with reports from the free press. Separate markets for a minority who are willing and able to pay on the one hand and for consumers of ad-funded free reports on the other would be risky for democracy – if only because fewer and fewer citizens would be motivated to actively participate in referendums and elections. Free media that are primarily ad-financed and that rely on coverage will hardly rely on complex, cost-intensive reporting.

It is also not clear how media organisations will manage to stand up to new intermediaries such as Facebook and Co. Journalism will be increasingly used on these platforms, where the selection of news items is based on a secret algorithm that is clearly different from criteria of journalistic relevance.

Independent media – enlightened society

There are no despots in Switzerland who jeopardise press freedom. But economic constraints are also risky in the medium term. The political challenge is to guarantee framework conditions for high-quality journalism.

Savings measures, consolidation processes, time pressure and turning away from journalism to new business fields are leading to financial and personal bloodletting in the editorial departments of the established media. But it takes in-depth, independent information for a form of government that is based on the involvement of all citizens to be able to function. In view of the changes in the media, there is therefore a pressing need for an infrastructure programme for journalism.

Safeguard sources of finance for quality journalism

It is possible that in future private media companies will no longer be in a position to supply sufficient resources for multifaceted and independent journalism. Politicians should therefore provide for measures to safeguard independent media services. Private media – whether online or offline – should be able to profit from direct media promotion. Promotional measures could relate to start-ups, investments or permanent operation. Public service broadcasting will take on an key function in the political process. Various studies – including that by TA-SWISS – confirm that the information it provides is balanced and well-founded. An independent public service provider must therefore be retained. For the SRG SSR to reach a young public as well, they must also provide an attractive online offering, and be able to offer innovative video and audio products. Conversely, the abandonment of advertising and sponsorship is justified. As a further

example, alternative ownership models – foundations, for instance – that remove the financial pressure from editorial teams could receive preferential tax treatment.

Promote media competence on a broad front

The media landscape is becoming increasingly complex and difficult to understand. Newspapers are entering into partnerships with each other and with providers of other services. Media competence covers considered relations with traditional media and social networks as well as knowledge of media ownership structures, the way journalism functions and the mechanisms of data collection.

Schools have a key role to play in empowering the young generation to correctly evaluate reports in the various media. But the public service providers must also commit themselves to explain the background to journalistic services to the public in detail.

Establish transparency

Anyone who reads a newspaper or takes any notice of a radio or television programme has to trust that the content is journalistically meaningful and has been prepared impartially. Ownership models and economic ties can, however, influence a medium's choice of topic. In any case, social media and search engines follow different relevance criteria from the traditional media, and they keep their algorithms secret. It is therefore still unclear why particular content is displayed.

Additionally, media and platforms that distribute information try to analyse the data of visitors to their offerings and hence to create user profiles; what happens to these is only rarely disclosed.

The media sector should therefore formulate ethical rules of conduct against the mixing of journalistic and commercial interests, and for transparency about ownership structures and the collection and use of data. New intermediaries should also be obliged to disclose their algorithms.

Access to technologies

Small and medium-sized media firms are hardly in a position to manage the necessary investments in digital technologies and know-how on their own. If platform operators or large media firms with technological solutions become providers for other media, it must be ensured that they do not favour their own company over their competitors. And the SRG SSR should offer to cooperate with private media in the technological field.

Citizens participate in the public debate

One of the responsibilities of journalism is to mediate between population and politicians and to bring citizens' concerns into the political process. It is certainly true that newspapers, as well as the SRG SSR, pick up the topics that preoccupy the population. However, the reporting is frequently episodic in nature; it would be necessary to place the preoccupations of the population increasingly and systematically into another context.

It is, however, also essential to utilise the new forms of journalism that enable interaction with the public via social networks and comments functions. Substantive discussions in online forums only come about if the journalists participate themselves and comments are moderated. This costs time and thus money; both have to be found, where appropriate with media policy support.

New instruments for measuring new offerings and forms of usage

Commercial media companies must be able to substantiate the use of their offerings to the advertising industry. To continue to achieve advertising revenue in the future, it is imperative to extend audience research from conventional offerings to include digital products. It is also essential to close the loopholes in commercial audience research. Today in particular, data on the media system that are irrelevant to the advertising industry are not collected at all, or are not published.

Politicians should regulate the closure of data gaps and public access to collected data, and the media sector must develop cross-media research into media and usage, together with new instruments for measuring online usage.

Study «Medien und Meinungsmacht»

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